

Complexes of Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) with Polydentate Schiff Base Ligand

B. K. SINHA^{*a}, M. KUMAR^b, RAJIV KUMAR^a and N. C. BHATTACHARJEE^a

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Magadh University, Bodh-Gaya-824 234

^bDepartment of Chemistry, J. J. College, Gaya-823 001

Manuscript received 14 June 1993, revised 9 December 1993, accepted 17 February 1994

Metal complexes of 4-amino-3,5-dimercapto-1,2,4-triazole have been studied earlier¹. In the present study an attempt has been made to investigate the donor behaviour of Schiff base of substituted-1,2,4-triazole. 4-Amino-3,5-dimercapto-1,2,4-triazole readily condenses with salicylaldehyde to form 4-salicylaldimino-3,5-dimercapto-1,2,4-triazole (H₂-saldt). Here we report the synthesis and characterisation of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes with H₂-saldt.

(A)

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) correspond to composition [M(H-saldt)₂] and [M(saldt)(H₂O)₃] (M = Co^{II} or Ni^{II}). The complexes in general are insoluble in water or common organic solvents, but fairly soluble in DMF. The complexes exhibit negligible molar conductance values (in DMF) supporting their non-ionic nature. The aquo complexes do not lose water below 120–130° indicating that water molecules are either coordinated or strongly bonded in the crystal lattice. Three different tautomeric forms are possible for the ligand. However, the ir spectra provide evidence in favour of the existence of ligand in thione form (A). The ligand displays broad ir

band at 3 180–2 960 cm⁻¹ attributed to hydrogen bond, OH and NH stretches of triazole ring. The absence of ν_{SH} band (2 650–2 450 cm⁻¹) is an evidence² in favour of structure (A). The bands at 1 620 and 1 395 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν_{N=CH} and δ_{OH} of phenolic proton. The band at 1 195 cm⁻¹ of the ligand is assigned³ to ν_{C-O} vibrations. The thioamide bands⁴ of the ligand are observed at 1 530, 1 485, 1 175 and 898 cm⁻¹. The ν_{N=CH} band for the metal complexes at 1 600 ± 5 cm⁻¹ indicate that aldimine nitrogen⁵ is involved in bonding in almost all the complexes. Phenolic ν_{C-O} vibration at 1 195 cm⁻¹ shifts to higher frequency by 20–30 cm⁻¹ and disappearance of δ_{OH} at 1 395 and ν_{OH} at 3 150 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes, suggest deprotonation and involvement of phenolic oxygen in bond formation. The aquo complexes display a broad and medium band around 3 400 cm⁻¹ and weaker bands around 750 and 650 cm⁻¹ assigned to OH stretching, rocking and wagging vibrations⁶ respectively, indicating coordination of water in aquo complexes. In the complexes thioamide bands⁴ are affected appreciably. The thioamide bands I and II attributable to ν_{C=N} + δ_{NH} are raised to higher frequencies indicating the involvement of thioamide group in bond formation. The thioamide bands III and IV originating from ν_{C-N} and ν_{C=S} vibrations are also affected. In the monoligated complexes, the former is raised to higher frequency by 30–50 cm⁻¹ while the latter to lower frequency by 120–130 cm⁻¹. The shift of thioamide band IV to lower frequency which is mainly due to ν_{C=S} vibration unambiguously suggests the coordination of thioamide group sulphur by deprotonation in thiol tautomer of the ligand. In case of the bisligated

complexes, the shift of $\nu_{C=S}$ band by 30–50 cm^{-1} suggests that the thioamide group is bonded through thione sulphur. From the above discussion tridentate nature (N, S and O donor atoms) of the ligand is indicated. In case of the bisligated complexes ligand is monoanionic and sulphur is bonded in thione tautomer, while in the monoligated complexes the ligand is dianionic and sulphur is attached to metal atoms by deprotonation in thiol-tautomer.

Cobalt(II) complexes, $[\text{Co}(\text{H-saltdt})_2]$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{saltdt})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ show μ_{eff} values of 4.93 and 5.13 B.M. respectively, as expected for spin-free octahedral cobalt(II) complexes⁷. These complexes exhibit two bands at 8 100–9 100 and 20 700–21 700 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to the transition ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} (P)$ respectively, in an approximate octahedral field⁸. The transition ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ is two-electron jump and usually very weak and therefore remains unobserved. The octahedral geometry is supported by the observed magnetic moments.

Nickel(II) complexes $[\text{Ni}(\text{H-saltdt})_2]$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{saltdt})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ show magnetic moment values of 3.03 and 3.26 B.M. respectively, indicating their six-coordinated octahedral geometry⁷. Low ϵ_{max} value of the complexes in electronic spectra indicates approximately octahedral environment of ligand molecule in the complex. The bands at 16 400–17 400 and 23 500–25 500 cm^{-1} are assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (P)$ transitions respectively⁹.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd (Colour, M p °C)	Analysis% . Found (Calcd.)			
	C	H	N	M
$\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{OS}_2$ (H_2 -saltdt) (Yellow-white, 227)	42.96 (42.85)	3.21 3.17	22.36 22.22)	—
$\text{Co}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}_4\text{OS}_2)_2$ (Brown, 265d)	38.42 (38.50)	2.41 2.46	19.88 19.96	10.42 10.50)
$\text{Co}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{N}_4\text{OS}_2) \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Brown, 281d)	29.70 (29.76)	3.23 3.30	15.37 15.43	16.18 16.23)
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}_4\text{OS}_2)_2$ (Yellow-green, 255d)	38.43 (38.52)	2.43 2.49	19.84 19.89	10.38 10.46)
$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{N}_4\text{OS}_2) \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Green, 275d)	29.68 (29.77)	3.24 3.30	15.40 15.43	16.09 16.18)

Experimental

All the chemicals were either of Extra pure (Merck) or AnalaR grade. C and H were analysed at Lucknow, and N was estimated by semimicro Duma's method. Metals were estimated by standard methods¹⁰. Electronic (dioxan) and ir spectra (CsI) of the complexes were recorded at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Gouy balance.

4-Salicylaldimino-3,5-dimercapto-1,2,4-triazole : A mixture of 4-amino-3,5-dimercapto-1,2,4-triazole¹¹ and salicylaldehyde (in equimolar ratio) in ethanol was refluxed for ~ 1 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (80%).

Preparation of complexes :

The complexes of the type $\text{M}(\text{H-saltdt})_2$ ($\text{M} = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ or Ni^{II}) were prepared by adding an aqueous solution of metal chloride or acetate (0.01 mol in 60 ml water) to aqueous ethanolic solution of ligand (0.02 mol in 100 ml 30% ethanol), and the resulting solution was refluxed on a steam-bath for 10–15 min. The resulting solid were washed with aqueous ethanol and dried over CaCl_2 . The complexes of type $\text{M}(\text{saltdt}) \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{M} = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ or Ni^{II}) were obtained immediately when an aqueous ethanolic solution of the metal chloride (0.01 mol in 60 ml 50% ethanol) was added slowly to an alkaline aqueous ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.01 mol ligand and 0.01 mol NaOH in 100 ml 50% ethanol), and the mixture digested on a steam-bath for a few minutes. The resulting solid products were washed with aqueous ethanol and dried over CaCl_2 and finally at 60–70° in an air-oven for 3–5 min.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. J. P. Srivastava, Professor and Head, Department of Chemistry and Dean, Faculty of Science, Magadh University, Bodh-Gaya, for facilities and discussions.

References

1. B. K. SINHA, R. SINGH, J. P. SRIVASTAVA AND L. K. MISHRA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 1797.
2. R. D. BEREMAN, D. M. BAIRD, J. BORDNER and J. DORFMAN, *Polyhedron*, 1983, **2**, 25.
3. S. J. GRUBER, C. M. HARRIS and E. SINN, *J. Inorg. Nucl.*

NOTE

- Chem.*, 1968 **30**, 1805
- 4 C N R RAO, R VENKATARAGHAVAN and T R KASTURI
Cand J Chem, 1964, **42**, 36, M AKBAR ALI and S
E LIVINGSTONE, *Coord Chem Rev*, 1974, **13**, 101, G
R BURNS, *Inorg Chem*, 1968, **7** 277
 - 5 C P PRABHAKARAN and C C PATEL, *J Inorg Nucl
Chem*, 1969, **31**, 3316
 - 6 P R SHUKLA, V K SINGH, A M JAISWAL and J NARAIN,
J Indian Chem Soc, 1983, **60**, 321
 - 7 B N FIGGIS and R S NYHOLM, *Prog Inorg Chem*,
1964 **6**, 37
 - 8 A B P LEVER, *Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy*, El-
sevier, Amsterdam, 1968
 - 9 C J BALLHAUSEN *Introduction to Ligand Field Theory*,
McGraw Hill, New York, 1962
 - 10 A I VOGEL, *A Text book of Quantitative Inorganic
Analysis*, Longmans Green, London 1978
 - 11 J SANDSTROM, *Acta Chem Scand*, 1961, **15**, 1295

